

Condensation of *o*-Hydroxy Aromatic Aldehydes with ω -Cyanacetophenone.

BY

SUBIMAL CHANDRA GHOSAL.

The work that is described in this paper was undertaken in the expectation of obtaining pyrilium derivatives containing the cyano group. For instance, salicylaldehyde, ω -cyanacetophenone and hydrochloric acid might react thus :—

(compare Decker and Fellenburg, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 3815; Perkin, Robinson and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1085; Robinson and collaborators, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1577 and subsequent papers). In no case did the reaction give the expected product.

The reaction between an *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and ω -cyanacetophenone gives a benzoyl coumarin: when salicylaldehyde is used the product is identical with the 3-benzoylcoumarin prepared by Knoevenagel and Arndt (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4497).

The formation of the coumarin derivatives is probably to be attributed to the interaction of the more reactive

ciano group with the phenolic hydroxy group according to the following scheme :—

As it frequently happens in condensation of this type that an intermediate imino compound is formed (Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 562), it appeared a matter of interest to examine whether by conducting the experiment in an anhydrous medium, so as to prevent the premature decomposition of the cyano group, the intermediate imino phase could be isolated. Experiments made in this direction, however, were unsuccessful.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Benzoylcoumarin.

Salicylaldehyde (3 g.) and *o*-cyanacetophenone (4 g.) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.). Dry hydrochloric acid was passed through the solution cooled to 0° for nearly four hours. The mixture was left overnight in a well-corked flask. Next morning the reddish brown contents were poured into a large excess of water and the solution was filtered from resinous matter. The filtrate on keeping deposited the condensation product in beautiful glistening needles. A further quantity was recovered from the resinous matter by treatment with dilute alcohol. The yield was 60 per cent. of the theoretical. When recrystallised from alcohol, it melted at 138° and was found to be identical with the 3-benzoylcoumarin described by Knoevenagel and Arndt (*loc. cit.*). (Found : C = 76.6 ; H = 4.00. C₁₆H₁₀O₃ requires C = 76.8 ; H = 4.00 per cent.)

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual manner, separated from alcohol as a yellow crystalline mass and melted at 95° - 100° with decomposition. (Found: $N=8.27$. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires $N=8.23$ per cent.)

6-Nitro-3-benzoylcoumarin.

3-Benzoylcoumarin (2 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.). The solution was cooled to 0° , and treated with 60 c.c. of a mixture of 1 part of strong nitric acid and 3 parts of concentrated sulphuric acid. At the end of half an hour the product was poured on crushed ice and the precipitated mass collected.

It was purified by recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid. It melted at 200° and was identified by direct comparison with a specimen synthesised for the purpose (see below). (Found: $N=4.91$. $C_{16}H_9O_5N$ requires $N=4.74$ per cent.)

The position of the nitro group in the product described above was established by condensing ω -cyanacetophenone (4 gms.) with 5-nitro-salicylaldehyde (4.5 gms.) in the usual manner. The product separated from a mixture of alcohol and acetone in pale yellow needles melting at 200° .

8-Methyl-3-benzoylcoumarin.

The reaction with *o*-homosalicylaldehyde was brought about exactly as in the case of salicylaldehyde. The product crystallised from dilute acetone in white feathery needles. It melted at 126° . (Found: $C=77.1$; $H=4.5$. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3$ requires $C=77.2$; $H=4.5$ per cent.) The

phenylhydrazone separated from alcohol as a yellow crystalline mass decomposing between 106° and 110° .

6-Methyl-3-benzoylcoumarin.

It was prepared in the usual way from *p*-homosalicylaldehyde (4 g.) and ω -cyanacetophenone (4 g.). The coumarin separated from alcohol in white needles and melted at 174° . (Found: C=77.00; H=4.5. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3$ requires C=77.2; H=4.5 per cent.)

7-Methyl-3-benzoylcoumarin.

7-Methyl-3-benzoylcoumarin was prepared in the usual way from *m*-homosalicylaldehyde (4 g.) and ω -cyanacetophenone (4 g.). The coumarin separated from alcohol in white needles and melted at 142° . (Found: C=77.01; H=4.48. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3$ requires C=77.2; H=4.5 per cent.)

The *phenylhydrazone* separated from alcohol in yellow crystalline mass decomposing between 115° and 120° .

7-Hydroxy-3-benzoylcoumarin.

The yield of the condensation product using resorcyaldehyde was unsatisfactory and only a small quantity

of it was obtainable after repeated treatment of the resinous product with dilute alcohol. It crystallised from alcohol in white needles; m. p. 241°. (Found: C=71·96; H=3·71. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$ requires C=72·18; H=3·75 per cent.)

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared by boiling the coumarin with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate in the usual way. It separated from alcohol in needle-shaped crystals melting at 172°. (Found: C=69·98; H=3·82. $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ requires C=70·12; H=3·89 per cent.)

3-Benzoyl-β-naphthapyrone.

The condensation with 1:2-naphtholaldehyde took place readily. The product, light yellow needles, on recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid melted at 215° and evidently consisted of the 3-benzoyl-β-naphthapyrone described by Kurt Bartsh (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1974). (Found: C=79·7; H=3·99. $C_{20}H_{12}O_3$ requires C=80·00; H=4·0 per cent.)

My best thanks are due to Principal H. E. Stapleton and Prof. R. N. Sen for their kind interest in the work.

Received, November 9, 1925.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE, CALCUTTA.